

Like an earlier work (3) this conclusion is drawn for the following reasons :

(A) No alcohol soluble phosphate is detected in the ground mixture of urea nitrate and cobalt phosphate.

(B) The results (Table 2) indicate that cobalt nitrate formed in the reaction increases with the increasing amount of urea nitrate and reaches a limiting value when the mole ratio of cobalt phosphate to urea nitrate is 1 : 2.

TABLE 2—COBALT NITRATE CONTENT IN ETHANOL EXTRACT
[Cobalt phosphate, 7.3358 g + urea nitrate]

Weight of urea nitrate (g)	Cobalt phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	Cobalt nitrate Found (g)	Cobalt nitrate Calculated (g)
1.23	1:0.50	0.2464	0.9146
2.46	1:1.00	1.4946	1.8293
3.69	1:1.50	2.5212	2.7439
4.92	1:2.00	3.3709	3.6585
6.15	1:2.50	3.3710	3.6585

(C) At the later stage of grinding the mixture forms a paste.

This investigation indicates that unavailable phosphatic minerals of iron or cobalt in acidic soils may be made available to plants by using urea nitrate.

References

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Studies on the Conditions of Formations of Heteropoly Decavanadocobaltates

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THE existence of $[\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}]^{6-}$ polyanion, depending upon vanadium ion concentration and pH has been reported¹ and the crystal structures of a few heteropoly complexes of this isopoly anion with Ca and Zn

as the heteroatom, have been elucidated². Chemical literature does not reveal any exhaustive studies on the formation of vanadocobaltate heteropoly complexes. The present communication deals with the conditions of formation and apparent molecular weight determinations of new heteropoly complexes: $(\text{NH}_4)_4 [\text{CoV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{H}_2 [\text{H}_2\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. These two heteropoly compounds, one being ammonium salt and the other being its free acid, have been formed with different concentrations of the reacting substances and at different pH.

Ammonium 10 Heteropolyvanadocobaltate (II) :

Solutions of arbitrary concentrations of the reactants, when mixed together, may cause immediate precipitation, leading to the formation of a compound with indefinite composition. When solution of .004 M cobaltous chloride and .05 M ammonium metavanadate were mixed together with 20 ml of glacial acetic acid, they did not give rise to immediate precipitation. So, 50 ml. of .05 M ammonium metavanadate mixed with 20 ml. of glacial acetic acid was gradually added by one ml. in each turn to 50 ml. of .004 M cobaltous chloride solution and an extensive study on the pH variation of the system was carried out as discussed in the previous detailed communications³. There was a gradual decrease in the pH of the solution up to the addition of 45 ml. of ammonium metavanadate and glacial acetic acid mixture. It was then followed by a plateau of constant pH of 4.5 up to 54 ml. of ammonium metavanadate reactant mixture. Thermometric titrations⁴ corroborated the above results. By comparing these two curves⁵ the range in volume of the reactants could be studied. So, 54 ml. of .05 M ammonium metavanadate - glacial acetic acid mixture was added to 50 ml. of .004 M cobaltous chloride solution with constant vigorous stirring and refluxed for one and half hour in a round bottom flask, evaporated to crystallisation and left in vacuum. After nine days interval of time light orange shining crystals were isolated from the mother liquor and were recrystallised from lukewarm water. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and instrumental methods. Vanadium was estimated colorimetrically by hydrogen peroxide method⁶. Cobalt was estimated gravimetrically⁷ weighing as CoSO_4 at 450-500. Nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by element estimation technique. (Found: Co, 3.98; V, 36; N, 3.85; H, 3.69; calcd. for $(\text{NH}_4)_4 [\text{CoV}_{10}\text{O}_{28}] 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Co, 4.16; V, 36.09; N, 3.96; H, 3.68%), as suggested by Evans for complex heteropoly anion $[\text{X}^n \text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}]^{(6-n)-}$.

10-Heteropolyvanadocobaltous (II) Acid :

In this case 50 ml. of .1M ammonium metavanadate mixed with 25 ml. of glacial acetic acid was gradually added to 50 ml. of .006 M cobaltous chloride solution and pH and thermometric studies of the system were done separately as discussed for the previous compound. By comparing the graphs the volume of the reactants, at which the constant pH 3.7 was maintained, was

found to be 40 ml. of .1M ammonium metavanadate-glacial acetic acid mixture and 50 ml. of .006 M cobaltous chloride solution. Hence for the isolation of the compound in the solid state, the said amount of the reactants were taken in a beaker and stirred vigorously for at least three hours at a controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. It was then evaporated to crystallisation in a water bath and left in vacuum. Deep orange red crystals were isolated after 14 days. It was recrystallised from hot water. The complete analysis of the compound was done. No traces of nitrogen was found in the element estimation technique. (Found: Co, 5.15; V, 44.95; H, 1.36; calcd. for $H_2[H_2V_{10}O_{28}]6H_2O$: Co, 5.31; V, 45.17; H, 1.41%). The compound was found to be a free acid of the heteropoly anion $[H_2CoV_{10}O_{28}]^{2-}$, in comparison to that of its previous ammonium salt. The basicity of the compound was determined by titrating it in borax solution and was found to be 2. To know, if all the hydrogen atoms are equally ionizable under the same condition, the above titration was done conductimetrically⁷. The two distinct breaks in the graph clearly indicated that two hydrogen atoms are equally ionizable.

Determination of Apparent Molecular Weight :

The cryoscopic method as has been applied successfully by Alexander⁸ and by Thilo and Krüger⁹ for molecular weight determination of certain inorganic polyacids and polyphosphates etc., in water and molten sodium sulfate decahydrate, has also been applied here for the determination of the approximate molecular weights of the compounds in the same condition, i.e., in water and molten sodium sulphate decahydrate. This determination showed the molecular weight of the compound to be 1367 and 1075 for $(NH_4)_4[CoV_{10}O_{28}]18H_2O$ and $H_2[H_2CoV_{10}O_{28}]6H_2O$ respectively as compared with the calculated values 1413 and 1129.

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Spectrophotometric Study of Uranium(VI) with 2-Hydroxy-5'-Halo Chalcone Chelate

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PERUSAL of literature reveals that ortho-hydroxy chalcones of biological importance¹⁻³, due to the presence of α : β unsaturated carbonyl group (-OC-CH=CH-), exhibit the ability of chelate formation⁴⁻⁶. The efficiency of chalcones for the spectrophotometric investigations of various metal cations such as Be(II)⁶, Fe(III)⁶ and Ge(IV)⁷ has been observed.

In view of the analytical applications of chalcones the present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability constant of uranium(VI) complexes with 2'-OH-5'-Cl (HCC), 2'-OH-5'-Br (HBC) and 2'-OH-4'-Me-5'-Cl (HMCC) which have not been studied so far. These reagents react instantaneously with uranyl ion and develop an orange colour. The chelates are highly stable and intensity of colour remains unchanged for a week.

Experimental

The solution of uranium (VI) was prepared by dissolving AnalaR uranyl nitrate in ethanol. The metal content was determined by the titrimetric method of Nadkarni et. al.⁹, which agreed with the gravimetric method¹⁰. 2'-OH-5'-Cl (HCC), m.p. 108°, prepared by the method of Keror, Yen and Reichstan¹¹ and 2'-OH-5'-Br (HBC), m.p. 107-103°, obtained by the method of Kostanecki and Ludwig¹². The 2'-OH-4'-Me-5'-Cl (HMCC), m.p. 141° was formed by usual method¹³. These chalcones were crystallized in ethanol.

Spectrophotometric measurements were done by using 'Bausch and Lomb' spectronic-20. All the observations were made at room temperature 25°.

Results and Discussion

Spectral curve : Absorbance spectra were recorded by mixing uranyl nitrate solution with reagent (HBC) in the ratio 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 against corresponding reagent-blank prepared under identical conditions. The maximum absorbance was found to occur at 435 nm showing the formation of only one complex. The same wave length was also found suitable in case of reagents (HCC) and (HMCC).

Effect of pH, time and temperature on the colour of the chelate :

Throughout the course of study the pH of the system was maintained 5.6 ± 0.2 as there was no change in the

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